

Test-Taking Strategies as Determinant of Students' Academic Performance in Mathematics Public Secondary Schools in Ekiti State

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Abstract:

The study examined test-taking strategies as determinant of students' academic performance in Mathematics public secondary schools in Ekiti State. The study specifically investigated the predictive strength of components of test-taking strategies such as using mnemonics, permutation, testwiseness and skimming test questions on academic performance of students in Mathematics. This research adopted a descriptive research of survey design. The population for this study consisted of all S.S.S 2 students in public secondary schools in Ekiti State. The sample for the study consisted of 177 S.S.S 2 students drawn from 6 public secondary schools in Ekiti State using multistage sampling procedure. Two instruments tagged Test-taking Strategies Questionnaire (TTSQ) and Performance Test in Mathematics (PTM) were used to collect data for the study. The instruments for the study were validated by experts in the area of Tests and Measurement. The reliability of the instruments was determined through the test re-test method. Coefficient values of 0.71 and 0.79 were obtained for TTSQ and PTM respectively. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using inferential statistics of simple regression analysis. The study revealed that components of test-taking strategies such as mnemonics ($R^2 = 0.327$), permutation ($R^2 = 0.229$), testwiseness ($R^2 = 0.316$) and skimming test questions ($R^2 = 0.193$) significantly

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contributed to the academic performance of students in Mathematics. The study concluded that test-taking strategies have impact on students' academic performance in Mathematics. It was recommended among others that students should be given adequate orientation through workshops to update their knowledge in the use of test-taking strategies.

Keywords: Mnemonics, Permutation, Testwiseness, Skimming, Performance, Mathematics,

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Introduction

Tests are usually designed to assess students' knowledge in particular content or materials. When other factors affect students' performance, test scores are no longer valid measures of students' knowledge or ability levels. A test can be defined as an instrument of measurement relating to human behaviour. A test is a measurement device or technique used to qualify behavior or aid in the understanding and prediction of behaviour. Indeed, Kolawole and Oluwatayo (2001) identified some vital purposes of reliable and valid test items including certification after completing a prescribed course of study, for diagnosing learning difficulties for selection into higher educational programme (aptitude test) for providing feedback on teaching-learning process, for gauging effectiveness of teaching methodology, for providing a basis for self-evaluation.

As Kpolovie (2012) noted not until a test is able to reflect the true attribute, characteristics and abilities of a student, then such a test is invalid. Unfortunately, with all the benefit of testing by revealing students' capabilities many students have independently branded themselves as not science oriented and incapable of undertaking mathematical related courses. Some who offer mathematical related courses have failed out of school, some have dropped, some have change their school, some have constantly change their mathematics teachers, some have lost confidence in themselves of being capable of solving any mathematics problem.

Students' poor performance in Mathematics could be attributed to so many factors among which are teaching strategies, teachers' attitude, lack of instructional materials students laziness but little or no attention has been given to what is happening during the conduct of Mathematics tests (Olofin & Olojo, 2022). Observing students taking Mathematics tests shows that some of the students who have adequate knowledge or have prepared well, do not perform well in their Mathematics tests. Some students start preparation early, and study well for the Mathematics test but their performance does not commensurate with the preparation. This could be as a result of inappropriate use or lack of Tests-taking strategies.

According to Cohen and Upton (2007), test-taking strategies are those test-taking processes which the respondents have selected and which they are conscious of, at least to some degree. Cohen (2006) classifies test-taking strategies into three types of language learner strategies, test-management strategies, and test-wiseness strategies. In order to get better scores, learners should know test-taking strategies which they can apply in language tests.

Tests-taking strategies are cognitive abilities to deal with any testing situation in appropriate manner and to know what to do during tests. Examples of these strategies are managing time effectively, surveying all questions before responding, solving easy questions first, checking and reviewing answers, underlying key words or concepts in questions, eliminating wrong options, and others. These strategies help students perform well in tests. Furthermore, so many studies and researchers have identified various strategies and techniques such as Strategies used before the tests, and Strategies used during the tests, which could be used to improve students' academic performance in Mathematics. However it seems as if most Mathematics students are ignorant of the strategies and the ones that are aware are not making use of these strategies appropriately.

Testing strategies help students translate their knowledge from classroom learning (McLellan & Craig 2019). Students who have or acquire test-taking strategies or skills will positively affect their testing competence and, hence, their academic performance. This is particularly true for low-ability students who perform better than expected. In fact, some argue that test-taking strategies are just as important as having the basic knowledge and information to answer the test questions (Langerquist 2012).

In explaining why females generally do better than males in mathematics classes but show poorer performance on tests, Kimball (2009) suggested that the difference in test-taking strategies (e.g. problem-solving Strategies) used by males and females could be the reason behind the difference in test performance. Gallagher (2012) studied sex differences in problem-solving strategies used by high-scoring examinees in the mathematical section of the Scholastic Aptitude Test (SAT). In one part of this study, Gallagher analyzed the relationship among students' performances in SATs, the types of strategies they used, their attitude toward mathematics and their test-taking strategies. A strong relationship was found between performance in mathematics and test-taking strategies.

Since test anxiety is a fairly common problem in college students, having test-taking strategies can be extremely useful in reducing this anxiety. Test-taking strategies used effectively help examinees cope with the problem of test anxiety. For example, Carraway (2017) investigated the effect of a test-taking strategies seminar on improving students' scores in tests and on reducing their level of anxiety related to tests. The results of this study indicated that students who participated in the seminar had lower test-anxiety levels and higher test scores than their matched peers who did not participate in the seminar.

Tests are usually designed to assess students' knowledge in particular content or materials. When other factors affect students' performance, test scores are no longer valid measures of students' knowledge or ability levels. Test-taking strategies can improve the overall validity of the test scores so that they accurately reflect what students really know. This could be done by ensuring that students lose points only because they do not know the information and not for unrelated reasons.

Research has proven that students who are taught test-taking strategies generally do better on high stakes testing and have a better attitude about taking test (Scruggs & Mastropieri, 2021). Students, who are test-wise, approach test-taking in a positive way and have less test anxiety. It is a known fact that test anxiety can be a factor that affects the student's attitude toward the test. Students who are test wise and knowledgeable about test strategies score higher because they have the needed skills to help them handle difficult problems.

Students are taking more and more standardized tests than ever before and the stakes keep getting higher. Test-taking strategies are important to familiarize the students with methods to use when answering questions. By teaching students about test-taking strategies, they develop confidence and are familiar with test formats. This might not be true for all students; especially those who have taken the graduation test several times and failed, but the perception that all students hate standardized test is not true.

Research states that the teacher's attitude toward standardized testing has a direct relationship on student achievement (Green, 2012). If teachers become more knowledgeable about standardized testing they can use the results to enhance their teaching and their

attitudes. Gulek (2003) believes that teachers should look at test preparation from an “instructional preparation practice standpoint; which will make teaching test-taking strategies effortless.” These high-stakes test can keep students from graduating or passing to the next grade level. The pressure for teachers to prepare their students to meet the demands of standardized tests can create a very negative atmosphere.

Iza and Gil (2015) describes mnemonic as memory-enhancing pedagogical methods aimed at improving learning and information recall through the use of imagery. A common criticism of mnemonics is that they only encourage rote memorization and do not help with higher order skills, such as comprehension or the transfer of knowledge. This criticism can be addressed with two responses.

Iza and Gil (2015) argued that although many teachers aspire for their students to be critical, insightful, curious, and deeply appreciative of the subject matter, education still requires a great deal of fact learning, which mnemonics can help with. Learning basic facts with mnemonics leaves more time for higher order learning. Permutation involves predicting questions for the next test. Some students write questions (different types) on each chapter/unit during private studying and likewise provide solution for such questions. Some students do poorly in test because of lack of ability to predict test questions.

Skimming is a technique that enables the reader to cover a vast amount of material very rapidly. Skimming is used to quickly identify the main ideas of a text. People often skim when they have lots of material to read in a limited amount of time. According to Sutz and Weverka (2015), when the readers skim a page, they take the main ideas from the reading material without reading all the words. The readers look for and seize upon words that appear to give the main meaning. Readers skim when time is short or when they need to understand the general ideas but not the particulars of an article or book. It takes three or four times faster than normal reading. According to Sutarsyah (2010), some of the words are not so important to understand that the readers may neglect them since they sometimes do not really connect to the idea being searched. The readers do not need to observe every single words in the text. Skimming takes place while reading and allows the readers to look for details in addition to the main ideas.

Testwiseness has been defined as the ability to respond advantageously to items containing extraneous clues and, therefore, to obtain credit without knowledge of the subject matter being tested. Similarly, Bachman (2010) defines testwiseness as a set of individual characteristics related to the amount and type of preparation or prior experience with a given test. They include the conscious pacing of one’s time, reading questions before the passage upon which they are based and ruling out as many alternatives as possible in multiple choice items and then guessing among the ones remaining. Testwiseness is an individual’s ability to improve his or her test score by recognizing and utilizing cues in the test multiple choice items, format or testing situation (Houston, 2015).

It is therefore necessary to examine test-taking strategies as determinant of students’ academic performance in Mathematics public secondary schools in Ekiti State. The researcher was of the opinion that if the method of teaching is improved but poor test-taking strategies by students, it could affect students’ performance in Mathematics. It is without doubt that some students prepare for Mathematics tests, but the problem is when do students start preparation and how do they prepare for Mathematics tests. It appears that some of the

students do not start preparation until few weeks to the Mathematics tests. Some students of course attend Mathematics classes, partake in all Mathematics class activities and do the assignments given to them but they appear not to study intensively until few days to their Mathematics tests which may in turn affect their performance in the Mathematics tests. The study specifically investigated the predictive strength of components of test-taking strategies such as using mnemonics, permutation, testwiseness and skimming test questions on academic performance of students in Mathematics.

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated for this research:

1. Using mnemonics do not significantly predict the academic performance of students in Mathematics.
2. Permutation do not significantly predict the academic performance of students in Mathematics.
3. Testwiseness do not significantly predict the academic performance of students in Mathematics.
4. Skimming test questions do not significantly predict the academic performance of students in Mathematics.

Methodology

This research adopted a descriptive research of survey design. The population for this study consisted of all S.S.S 2 students in public Secondary Schools in Ekiti South Senatorial district of Ekiti State. The sample for the study consisted of 177 S.S.S 2 students drawn from 6 public secondary schools in Ekiti State. The sample was selected using multistage sampling procedure.

In stage one, two Local Governments were randomly selected through balloting method from the senatorial district in Ekiti State. In stage two, three public secondary schools were selected through stratified random sampling technique from each of the two local governments chosen for the study. In stage three, 177 S.S.S. 2 students were selected from the 6 public secondary schools using proportionate stratified random sampling technique.

Two instruments tagged Test-taking Strategies Questionnaire (TTSQ) and Performance Test in Mathematics (PTM) were used to collect relevant data for the study. Both instruments consisted of two sections namely Section A and B. *Section A* of the TTSQ sought for demographic information about the respondents while Section B consisted of 16 items to elicit information on components of test taking strategies. The continuum was using the 5 point Likert type - Very Much Like (VM); Much Like (ML); Unlike (UL); Very Much Unlike (VMU); and Not Sure (NS) which were scored 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively. The Performance Test in Mathematics (PTM) consisted of 30 objective test items in Mathematics

The instruments for the study were validated by experts in the area of Tests and Measurement. The experts determined its face and content to ensure the appropriateness of the instruments in measuring what they are supposed to measure.

The reliability of the instruments was determined through the test re-test method in two secondary schools outside the sampled area. The schools shared similar characteristics with the sample schools. The instruments were administered twice on 20 respondents in two schools within interval of two weeks. The data collected on the two administrations were

collated and analyzed using the Pearson's Product Moment Correlation analysis. Co-efficient values of 0.71 and 0.79 were obtained for TTSQ and PTM respectively.

The researcher visited the sampled schools in each of the selected local government areas to administer the research instruments. The researcher personally visited each of the school sampled to administer the instruments with the help of two trained research assistants. The instruments were administered on Mathematics students and retrieved immediately after the respondents have responded to the instruments. The researcher's personal contact and visit to the respondents helped in ensuring better understanding of the instruments and also ease retrieval of the instruments.

The data collected through the instruments were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using inferential statistics of simple regression analysis.

Results

Hypothesis 1: Using mnemonics do not significantly predict the academic performance of students in Mathematics.

In testing this hypothesis, data on mnemonics sub-variable of test-taking strategies were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section B of TTSQ (item 1 – 4) in the questionnaire. Data on students' academic performance were collected from the Performance Test in Mathematics (PTM). Both were compared for statistical significance using Simple Regression Analysis at 0.05 level of significance. The result is presented in table 1.

Table 1: Simple regression analysis between mnemonics and academic performance of students in Mathematics

Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Stand. Coefficients	t- Stat.	R	R ²	F
	(B)	Std Error	(Beta)				
Constant	0.221	0.764	-	0.290	0.572	0.327	110.145
Mnemonics	0.674	0.057	0.572	11.796			

In table 1, the calculated F-value of 110.145 is significant at $P < 0.05$, therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. It implies that using mnemonics significantly predicted the academic performance of students in Mathematics. The result of the analysis shown in Table 1 indicated the predictors accounted for 32.7 percent of the students' performance in Mathematics ($R^2 = 0.327$). It contributed 57.2% to the criterion variable in predicting students' academic performance in Mathematics.

The regression equation derivable from table 1 is $Y = 0.221 + 0.674X$

where:

Y = Students' academic performance in Mathematics

X = Mnemonics

Hypothesis 2: Permutation do not significantly predict the academic performance of students in Mathematics.

In testing this hypothesis, data on permutation sub-variable of test-taking strategies were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section B of TTSQ (item 5 – 8) in the questionnaire. Data on students' academic performance were collected from the Performance Test in Mathematics (PTM). Both were compared for statistical significance using Simple Regression Analysis at 0.05 level of significance. The result is presented in table 2.

Table 2: Simple regression analysis between permutation and academic performance of students in Mathematics

Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Stand. Coefficients	t- Stat.	R	R ²	F
	(B)	Std Error	(Beta)				
Constant	-0.885	1.093	-	-0.810	0.479	0.229	82.114
Permutation	0.898	0.097	0.479	9.225			

In table 2, the calculated F-value of 82.114 is significant at $P < 0.05$, therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. It implies that permutation significantly predicted the academic performance of students in Mathematics. The result of the analysis shown in Table 2 indicated the predictors accounted for 22.9 percent of the students' performance in Mathematics ($R^2 = 0.229$). It contributed 47.9% to the criterion variable in predicting students' academic performance in Mathematics.

The regression equation derivable from table 2 is $Y = -0.885 + 0.898X$

where:

Y = Students' academic performance in Mathematics

X = Permutation

Hypothesis 3: Testwiseness do not significantly predict the academic performance of students in Mathematics.

In testing this hypothesis, data on testwiseness sub-variable of test-taking strategies were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section B of TTSQ (item 9 – 12) in the questionnaire. Data on students' academic performance were collected from the Performance Test in Mathematics (PTM). Both were compared for statistical significance using Simple Regression Analysis at 0.05 level of significance. The result is presented in table 3.

Table 3: Simple regression analysis between testwiseness and academic performance of students in Mathematics

Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Stand. Coefficients	t- Stat.	R	R ²	F
	(B)	Std Error	(Beta)				
Constant	0.368	0.772	-	0.477	0.562	0.316	108.319
Testwiseness	0.664	0.058	0.562	11.486			

In table 3, the calculated F-value of 108.319 is significant at $P < 0.05$, therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. It implies that testwiseness significantly predicted the academic performance of students in Mathematics. The result of the analysis indicated the predictors accounted for 31.6 percent of the students' performance in Mathematics ($R^2 = 0.316$). It contributed 56.2% to the criterion variable in predicting students' academic performance in Mathematics.

The regression equation derivable from table 3 is $Y = 0.368 + 0.664X$

where:

Y = Students' academic performance in Mathematics

X = Peer Tutoring

Hypothesis 4: Skimming test questions do not significantly predict the academic performance of students in Mathematics.

In testing this hypothesis, data on skimming test questions sub-variable of test-taking strategies were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section B of TTSQ (item 13 – 16) in the questionnaire. Data on students' academic performance were collected from the Performance Test in Mathematics (PTM). Both were compared for statistical significance using Simple Regression Analysis at 0.05 level of significance. The result is presented in table 4.

Table 4: Simple regression analysis between skimming test questions and academic performance of students in Mathematics

Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Stand. Coefficients	t- Stat.	R	R ²	F
	(B)	Std Error	(Beta)				
Constant	2.253	0.841	-	2.679	0.439	0.193	61.801
Skimming Test Questions	0.560	0.068	0.439	8.274			

In table 4, the calculated F-value of 61.801 is significant at $P < 0.05$, therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. It implies that skimming test questions significantly predicted the academic performance of students in Mathematics. The result of the analysis indicated the predictors accounted for 19.3 percent of the students' performance in Mathematics ($R^2 = 0.193$). It contributed 43.9% to the criterion variable in predicting students' academic performance in Mathematics.

The regression equation derivable from table 4 is $Y = 2.253 + 0.560X$

where:

Y = Students' academic performance in Mathematics

X = Skimming Test Questions

Discussion

The study revealed that components of test-taking strategies such as mnemonics, permutation, testwiseness and skimming test questions significantly contributed to the academic performance of students in Mathematics with mnemonics as the highest

contributor to students' academic performance in Mathematics followed by testwiseness while skimming test questions was the least contributor to students' academic performance in Mathematics. The reason for this finding might be because of the submission of Iza and Gil (2015) who described mnemonic as memory-enhancing pedagogical methods aimed at improving learning and information recall through the use of imagery. Each mnemonic is designed to help remember a specific kind of information and it also aids retention. This finding is in consonance with the findings of Hammad (2010) and Iza and Gil (2015) who concluded that components of test-taking strategies used before test significantly contributed to the academic performance of students.

Students who are test wise can outperform students of equal ability who lack test-wiseness. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Abu Hashim (2012), Hamadneh (2016), Al-Mutlaq (2015) and Hammad (2010) who concluded that components of test-taking strategies such as testwiseness and skimming test questions used during test significantly contributed to students' academic performance.

Conclusion

It can be concluded that test-taking strategies have impact on students' academic performance in Mathematics. It is concluded that mnemonics, permutation, testwiseness and skimming test questions contribute to students' academic performance in Mathematics.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made.

1. The use of test-taking strategies should be incorporated into Mathematics class in secondary schools because it improves students' academic performance and boost students' confidence in writing tests and examinations in Mathematics.
2. Students should be given adequate orientation through workshops to update their knowledge in the use of test-taking strategies.
3. Students should adopt a positive attitude to test-taking strategies in Mathematics as this will go a long way to reduce their test anxiety and improve their confidence in answering test questions in Mathematics.

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